

Insecurity in the North-East and South-East of Nigeria: Implications for Socio-Economic Development

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Abstract: The paper examined the implications of insecurity in the Northeast and Eastern part of Nigeria for socio-economic development. The threat caused by Boko Haram, JAS and ISWAP in the North-East and the threat caused by ESN/IPOB in the South-East were found to be incongruous to socio-economic development in the areas where they operate. The paper is of the view that terrorism and terrorism related activities takes the form of violence, armed attacks, assault, aggravated assault, bombing, hijacking, or hostage taking, kidnapping, and killings. The paper adopted the conflict theory of Karl Marx and the secondary research method that relies on the use of existing articles and data sourced from the internet, and books. The paper recommends that government should fortify the law enforcement agents with latest equipment to boost security in the North-East and South-East in order to enhance safety and security, to allow for peace and socio-economic development in the areas where terrorists operate. Government should also engage the ESN/IPOB in constructive dialogue to address the Monday sit-at-home order, release Nnamdi Kanu to douse tension to allow for peace, security and socio-economic development in the South-East, Nigeria. It also recommends that government should encourage industrialists to provide jobs for the teeming jobless youths, and also raise awareness on the threat and consequences of terrorism and terrorism related activities to discourage some young people from joining violent groups.

Keywords: *Insecurity, Terrorism, Boko Haram, ISWAP, ESN/IPOB, Socio-Economic Development and Nigeria.*

Introduction

The North-East and South-Eastern part of Nigeria has been in the news, but the news is not a good one. The regions have suffered unprecedented violence leading to heavy losses in the socio-economic sector. The North-East region of Nigeria, comprises six states, namely, Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba, and Yobe. The is commonly known as the Hausa-Fulani ethnic groups. The people in this region are majorly farmers, and are known for trading in cows, and some other commercial activities. The South-East on the other hand composed of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo state, commonly known as Igboland. The people of the South-East are industrious, and known for agriculture, commercial and trading activities. For example, Apindi and Simwa (2023) declared that Anambra state have the lowest poverty rate in Nigeria. Lately, these states are plague with violence which has massively affected the socio-economic development of the regions.

A lot has happened in the regions, and the outcome is chaotic, and still deteriorating. What was alleged by the people, and governments as mere religious crisis in the North-East, and political protest over perceived marginalisation in the South-East has engulfed into dangers of

insecurity, and environment of socio-economic downturns. The downturns are caused by criminals who carry out acts of terrorism, and terrorism related activities. They are audacious, lethal and devious. Their activities are threats to humanity, peace and development in these regions.

Since the beginning of Boko Haram, and since she split into two factions, in 2016 - the Jam'atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda'adatiwa-Jihad (JAS), and Islamic State-West Africa Province (ISWAP) also known as (ISIS-WA), in the North-East; and the Independent People of Biafra (IPOB), the proscribed separatist group Eastern Security Network (ESN), and the so called "Unknown Gun Men (UGM) in the South-East; fear continue to immerse the whole of Nigeria, because, they are known for chaos, and annihilation. They use instruments of terrorism, violence, fear, armed robbery, arms and ammunitions, kidnapping, and known to be major cause of insecurity, property damage, and deaths of some innocent victims in places where they operate. Bastian, Veronika, Hannah, Joe, Edward, and Max (2023) assert that terrorism take several forms, including armed assault, bombing, hijacking, or hostage taking, kidnapping; and their nefarious activities is a big concern for people all over the world. These infamous cliques known for violence, and threats, to

a very large extent are also known to be the cause of food scarcity, hunger, poverty, joblessness, business downturn, and lack of access to education in many parts of the North-East, and to a large extent cause of minimal access to education and healthcare, and economic downturn, especially on Mondays in the South-East, in the case of the IPOB.

The focus of this paper is not on the factors that led the non-state actors into violence, that made the groups to be designated as terrorists, but the act of terrorism perpetrated by them, to the extent that the socio-economic well-being of the regions where they operate is in ruin. Access to academic activities, night life, access to healthcare, tourism, and economic activities are grounded, and in some cases in slow motion gasping for air, and seemed to run out of gas, because of the many troubles, and complications caused by their acts of criminalities. For some time now, the violence continues to border the regions, and threaten the country, but the Nigerian government seemed to be handling the violence with kids' gloves, because her efforts have not yielded the needed positive result. This review examined the impact of insecurity caused by terrorism and terrorism related activities on the socio-economic

development of the North-East and South-East of Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

Insecurity

The concept of insecurity means different thing to different people. For some, it connotes the lack of safety; danger, anything that has the potential to cause harm, doubt; absence of protection. Ejirefe and Onwordi (2025) conceptualise insecurity as a breakdown security, absence of circumstances that brings peace and joy, be it socio-economic, cultural, political that leads to conscious destruction of lives and property. Baland (2005) refers to insecurity as a state of fear or anxiety due to absence or lack of protection. Achumba, Ighomereho and Akpor-Rabaro (2013) define insecurity as the state of being open or subject to danger or threat of danger, where danger is the condition of being susceptible to harm or injury. Furthermore, Achumba et al (2013) state that, insecurity is the state of being exposed to risk or anxiety, where anxiety is a vague unpleasant emotion that is experienced in anticipation of some misfortune. Insecurity present itself in various forms as terrorism, terrorism related activities, such as killings, armed robbery, bombs, armed assault,

kidnapping, hostage-taking, destruction of property, etc. People who live in the North-East and South-East of Nigeria are exposed to these insecurities caused by terrorism and terrorism related violence.

Terrorism

Bastian et al, (2023) define terrorism as the use of violence to intimidate or coerce in the pursuit of political or ideological goals. It is usually understood to be done by non-state actors, such as individuals, or organisations not part of the government. Similarly, Schmid (2015) define terrorism as an anxiety inspiring method of repeated violent action, employed by (semi) clandestine individual, group or state actors, for idiosyncratic, criminal or political reasons, whereby in contrast to assassination the direct target of violence are not the main target, the immediate human victims of violence are generally chosen randomly (target of opportunity) or selectively (representative or symbolic targets) from a target population, and serve as message generators. Similarly, Boaz (2001) conceptualise terrorism as the deliberate use of violence against civilians in order to attain political, ideological and religious aims. In this paper, terrorism refers to any form of violence that leads to physical intimidation, assault, aggravated assault, death to achieve religious, economic, political aim, etc. Terrorism can

be aimed at individuals or civilians, country, or individual property, government property or public infrastructure.

Terrorism related Activities

This refers to deliberate use of destructive power or violence by individuals, groups or non-state actors, to make people afraid in order to achieve their ideology, such as political, economic, social, cultural, religious, violent extremism, or otherwise; through the instrument of wickedness such as killings, bomb blast, kidnapping, hostage-taking, armed robbery, aggravated assault, arson, cattle rusting, destruction of property, etc. For example, these activities are carried out by violent groups such as the IPOB, and the proscribed separatist group Eastern Security Network (ESN), and the so called “Unknown Gun Men (UGM); other terrorists’ groups such as Boko Haram, also known as “Jama atu Ahlissuma Lidda Awatiwal-Jihad” an Arabic phrase which means “People committed to the propagation of the Prophet’s teaching and Jihad”. For example, JAS, and ISWAP, specialises in using violence to commit crimes such as kidnapping, robbery, extortion, killings, etc.

Socio-economic Development

Litwinski (2017) conceptualise socio-economic development as a process of quantitative and qualitative structural changes that are a result of actions of subjects taken within social (economic) practice. The changes include increase in life situations, material conditions, economic structure and entrepreneurship, easy access to public goods, and services; especially changes in educational system and relations within the social system such as security, integration and trusts. Additionally, Castro (2018) Conceptualises social-economic development as a process that seeks to identify both the social and economic needs within a community, and seeks to create strategies that will address those needs in ways that are practical and in the best interests of the community over the long run.

Empirical Studies

Vasco, Azad and Di Maio (2019) state that Boko Haram targeted the Nigerian education system, assaulting schools, students and teachers in Northern Nigeria and disrupting access to education, and social services, especially for young people. Teachers were threatened, and in some cases, killed. Schools were damaged and destroyed, and often transformed into shelters for internal displaced people

(IDP); and the schools that remain in operation across Borno, Adamawa and Yobe State are overcrowded and unable to meet the needs of the host population and the IDP. Similarly, Human Right Watch (2012) states that Boko Haran attacked and destroyed at least 12 schools in and around Maiduguri, the capital of Borno State leaving several thousand children without access to education. Attacks on these schools put the life of both students and teachers in danger; and as well deprived student access to western education and teachers' access to work. Unfortunately, and unknown to Boko Haram, many of the students in Quranic schools stopped going to school out of fear of being recruited, because the terrorists' group were recruiting members from some of the Quranic schools. Abdullahi (2023) state that Zabarmari - a farming community famous for rice production was attacked by Boko Haram terrorists. Boko Haram storm the village on several motorbikes and attacked the farmers who were harvesting their farm input in the village of Koshebe, Karkut and Bulabulin in Mafa local government area, less than 20 kilometers from Maiduguri, the Borno State capital. During the attack the terrorists used knives to stab the farmers and killed 9 farmers. Abdul also stated that in November 2020, about 45 Zabarmari farmers were killed at

Kwashabe village, about 20 kilometres north of Maiduguri.

International Centre for Investigative Reporting (2023) investigation on the impact of the IPOB political protests strategy otherwise known as the Monday Sit-at-home on the South-East, and by virtue of reliance on figures from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Nigeria's Data Agency, and the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) 2021 survey reports. The ICIR investigation focused on nano and micro businesses, which made up 96.9% (38.413 million) of the 39.654 million MSMEs in Nigeria. In line with the survey, people interviewed were in the informal (untaxed and unregulated) sector. The survey, shown that SMEDAN/NBS report indicate that there were 1,297 million micro/nano enterprises in Anambra State and 764,844 in Abia State. Enugu State was estimated to have 1,154 million micro/nano enterprises, while Ebonyi had 561,287 businesses, and Imo State had 1,231 million micro/nano businesses. From the calculations, the South-East lost about N75,704 billion every Monday on nano and micro businesses. By this calculation, Anambra State lost N38.140 billion, Enugu N9.334 billion, Imo N13.739 billion, Ebonyi N4.079 billion, and Abia N10.412 billion. This whopping loss

does not include the entire businesses in the economy.

Morgen (2021) investigated the perception and impact of IPOB ordered seat-at-home protests on socio-economic activities in the South-East, Nigeria. The study used survey design via questionnaire, and find out that, the order has negative impact on the socio-economic development of the South-East region, because, it suspended commercial activities, which include banking operations, and other productive businesses. Similarly, Gbenemene (2022) study examine the impact of IPOB activities on socio-economic development of the South-East of Nigeria. The study used qualitative data from different documented evidence, and found that IPOB agitation/strategy have caused serious security challenges, especially on movement of people and goods, education, and government facilities; and it also affected markets operations in the region (Owoeye, Ezeanyi & Obiegbunam, 2022). Additionally, PLAC (2022) report shows that the

Theoretical Framework

Conflict Theory

The Karl Marx (1818-1883) theoretical underpinning was adopted to analyse this

paper. Karl Marx's conflict theory assumes that society is characterised by self-interest. The second assumption was that society operate under perpetual scarcity of resources. The third assumption was that, conflict is universal and cannot be avoided within social groups and between social groups (<https://en.wikipedia>). This theory relates to the present study in the sense that it shows the nature of the Nigerian society of domination, where the rich political-economic class continues to dominate the poor down trodden. This situation continues to breeds the conflict that makes Boko Haram, JAS, and ISWAP, ESN/IPOB continues to maim, destroy, kill and fight back to the extent of causing chaos to the socio-economic well-being of the regions where they operate.

Research Methodology

The article adopted secondary research method that relies on the compilation of existing data sourced from the internet, published works and books.

Description of implications of insecurity in the north-east and south-east on socio-economic development

The issue of insecurity caused by Boko Haram terrorism, JAS, ISWAP and IPOB, and consequences on Nigeria's socio-

economic development are phenomenal issues this paper seeks to analyze. In the first place, the Nigeria education system is patterned along the western kind of education which the religious terrorists don't like; hence they are rebelling against it. This explains one of the reasons why Boko Haram split faction - JAS kidnapped the Chibok girls on April 14, 2014 (Ejirefe, 2014). Offiong (2014) cited in Ejirefe (2014) assert that the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) statistics report that Nigeria has 10.5 million out of school cases and the bulk of this is from North-East. The incessant bombing of schools, killings and abduction of students, and their teachers in the North, especially in the North-East by Boko Haram, and recently her split terrorist groups, foretells grave threat for the development of the educational systems in North-East of Nigeria. Unfortunately, the incessant kidnapping and frequent disruption of the school system has made parents to prefer keeping their children at home. Currently, schools are deserted, because many teachers, and students are no longer interested in going back to the classroom, due to the insecurity. A situation, where parents and their children, and many teachers loose interest in education portends danger for the educational system.

Education drives development, because it produces nations builders such as engineers, lawyers, doctors, business people, economics, producers in all spheres, and marketers, both social, economic and political development, that brings good governance and good life to the people. Once this foundation - education, is destroyed, what you will have is poor harvest that would manifest in the form of food insecurity, poor healthcare, bad roads, poor housing, and poor transportation systems, poor administrators, and little or no development. Obviously, without meaningful education, development in the socio-economic spheres is far behind. ISWAP for instance, according to an IDP's returnee, forced farmers residents in many parts of Borno to pay tax to allow them to cultivate farm, and failure to pay tax means grave danger which in most cases result to death; consequently, many residents of Kukawa, and Monguno were killed while some had to run and relocate (Abdulkareem, 2022). Instead of paying such tax to government for the development of the community, it was forcefully collected for the self-aggrandisement of terrorists; the death of the innocent in the environment also means loss of human and economic resources, and so is many parts of the

North-East, because without security and people, socio-economic development is lost.

Implication of Insecurity on Socio-Economic Development of the South-East

The IPOB protests have very serious implications for the socio-economic development of the South-East. These include the inability of the people to operate their businesses due to fear of being killed, especially on Monday when the sit-at-home order is strictly enforced. Every Monday, traders, business men and business women lock their shops, shopping malls, fuel stations are closed; both human and vehicular movements were restricted, such that nobody dare move around and no vehicle other states in Nigeria dare passes through any route in the South-East, otherwise, their goods will be destroyed, the transportation vehicles, drivers and passengers, may be burnt alive. Adonu (2021) states that in Enugu where the sit-at-home order was strictly enforced, some people stayed at home, while some residence went about businesses, with major markets, transporters, banks and public institutions, including government ministries, and public schools recorded little or no activities. In some cases, members of the ESN/IPOB ensure they sabotage businesses of those who

disobeyed the sit-at-home order. For example, Punch News (2021) state that on Monday September 27, 2021, members of the IPOB set ablaze a bus transporting tomatoes, vegetable, and other foodstuffs to Enugu for violating the sit-at-home order.

Amnesty International (2025) report state that insecurity in the South-East Nigeria perpetrated by IPOB/ESN has negatively impacted people in the region, that the enforcement of the seat -at-home order issued on 9 August 2021, has led to human rights violations with people beaten or even killed for defying the order. 400 people in Imo state were killed between January 2019 and December 2021; and 1,844 people killed between January 2021 and June 2023. School have been shut, exams disrupted, forcing children to stay away from schools, and markets closed with harsh economic consequences for communities across the region. Similarly, PLAC (2022) report reveals that the clash between Nigerian security personnel and the ESN/IPOB members on August 23, 2021 led to the death of 2 security personnel and up to 21 civilians in Enugu state, and between 2015 to 2016 at least 150 IPOB members were killed.

Conclusion

Globally, security, peace and development are needed to guarantee meaningful life, but this is not the case when terrorism happen to a country. Nobody, no country has ever said anything good about terrorism. It has always been tails of woes, violence and deaths. Terrorism takes several forms, such as armed assault, bombing, suicide bombing, kidnapping, aeroplane hijacking, hostage taking, assassinations, etc. Their devastating activities are colossal concern for people, a world-wide phenomenon and a torn in the flesh of humankind. Terrorists are known for violence and are known to be one of the major causes of deaths since their inception, and such barbaric act impedes development. Global terrorism index, shows that terrorist activities are waning in the advanced or rather developed world, but continues to increase in Nigeria due to the devastating threats caused by Boko Haram and her splitter groups - JAS and ISWAP that has left life and property belonging to individuals, group and government destroyed, little or no access to education, little or no access to economic activities and the shortage of peace in North-Eastern Nigeria, and spill over effects of fear in other parts of Nigeria. On the other hand, the activities of ESN/IPOB in the South-East also left socio-economic development crawling, every Monday, especially in Onitsha, Aba,

Enugu, Owerre, and Abakaliki in Ebonyi state due to the Monday sit-at-home protest day, where schools, banks, human and commercial activities are put to a hurt. ESN/IPOB caused so much death and left many impoverished, and socio-economic development crawling.

Recommendations

1. Government should fortify the law enforcement agents with latest equipment to boost security in the North-East and South-East in order to enhance safety and security, to allow for peace and socio-economic development in the areas where terrorists operate.
2. Government should engage the ESN/IPOB in constructive dialogue to address the Monday sit-at-home order, release Nnamdi Kanu to douse tension to allow for peace, security and socio-economic development in the South-East, Nigeria.
3. Government should encourage industrialists to provide jobs for the teeming jobless youths, and also raise awareness on the threat and consequences of terrorism and terrorism related activities to discourage some young people from joining violent groups.

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